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INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES - TO THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IT IS THE BEGINNING OF THE TRANSITION

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Abstract: The article seeks to highlight the essence of information technology, their role in the transition to a digital economy and some of the issues that need to be addressed in the current process of globalization in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and draws some personal conclusions based on the tasks. Full presentation of the socio-economic potential of the digital economy and its introduction into all sectors of the national economy remains the most pressing issue today. It is to reveal the essence of these processes and to carry out work in this direction in accordance with the requirements of the time.

Keywords: information environment, information structure, information technology, computer technology, information and communication technology, electronic technology, digital technology, digital economy, internet, artificial intelligence.

Introduction

Full presentation of the socio-economic potential of the digital economy and its introduction into all sectors of the national economy remains the most pressing issue today. It is to reveal the essence of these processes and to carry out work in this direction in accordance with the requirements of the time.

At the same time, given the international importance of information technology in the current context of globalization, further development of cooperation with the world community and the introduction of advanced achievements are required to develop the digital sector as much as possible.

In recent years, various groups of experts from around the world have been proposing highly effective and up-to-date proposals on advanced development modules, including the development of each country's national economy on the basis of digital technologies. Without it, humanity could be left without the benefits of digital technology.

The results achieved in the field of digital technologies in the world in a short period of time are leading to radically new changes in the activities of people, companies, firms and organizations. As a result of these efforts, the world's population has greater access to computers and the Internet and access to their services. After all, it is much harder to imagine our lives today without computers and internet services.

It is becoming a natural process for the digital economy to serve the common interests of the people and to cover all aspects on a large scale. Such an economy provides many new knowledge and skills, requires radically new measures of social protection, a qualitatively new relationship between work and leisure.

The search for new solutions requires the cooperation of governments, civil society, political circles, and the scientific community to create modern technologies. Every day, we witness a growing body of evidence on how digital technologies contribute to peacebuilding, the expansion of human rights, and sustainable development for the benefit of society as a whole.

In our country, comprehensive measures are being taken to actively develop the digital economy, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and industries, especially in public administration, education, health, industry and agriculture. The adoption of the National Program on October 5, 2020 by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Strategy" Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 "and measures for its effective implementation" is a clear proof of our opinion.

According to the program, more than 220 priority projects have been launched to improve the e-government system, further develop the local market of software products and information technologies, establish IT parks in all regions of the country, as well as provide qualified personnel for all sectors of the national economy. Such positive changes will undoubtedly serve for a more prosperous and prosperous life of our people.

Analysis of the relevant literature

Fitzsimmons, James A., and Mona J. Fitzsimmons (Service Management: Operations, Strategy, Information Technology, (6th ed.)), McGraw-Hill / Irwin, 2006; ISBN-13: 978-007-126346-7, and ISBN-10: 007-126346-2. Strategies for the 21st Century. McGraw Hill), IT SERVICE MANAGEMENT A Guide for ITIL ® Foundation Exam Candidates Second Edition Ernest Brewster, Richard Griffiths, Aidan Lawes, John Sansbury - 2012), Australian School of Business Information Systems, Technology and Management. 2013, Professor Charles Fine Massachusetts Institute of Technology Sloan School of Management Cambridge, Massachusetts 02142, September 2010, Service Operations 15.768, Utkin V.B., Baldin K.V. (Informatsionnye sistemy i tekhnologii v ekonomike.-Uchebnoe posobie.- M.: UNITI, 2008), Kozirov A.A. (Information technologies in economics and management.-M.: 2009), Gromov G.R. (Informatsionnye tehnologii epxi Interneta.-M.: Nauka, 2004) and others.

Among our local scientists on information technology issues in Uzbekistan Gulomov SS, Abdullaev OM (Modern information systems and technologies in the economy.-T .: Impress Media, 2018, Gulomov S.S. et al. Blockchain technologies in the digital economy.-T., 2019, Abdullaev OM (Digital economy.-T. , 2020).

Research methodology

As a result of our research, information technologies, published literature on their content, relevant laws, legal documents and other sources were studied, based on which relevant opinions were formed and methods of scientific observation, logical thinking, analysis and synthesis were used.

Analysis and results

In this article, we want to focus on issues related to the transition to a digital economy based on the development of information technology. Information technology is one of the main sources of the modern information bank of the national economy of each country. With the development of technology and new technologies, information technology in the collection and processing of relevant data has gone through several stages of its development.

As a result of the rapid development of science and technology, increasing the quality and reliability of data, the role of information technology in all sectors of the national economy has sharply increased.

Information technology is the first foundation of the transition to the digital economy. It would be more accurate to call it digital information technology, because information technology is based on relevant numbers. Their evolution is divided into several stages. Clearly, the emergence and development of digital information technology is an objective process driven by the demands of society's development.

Today, the main goal of the promotion of digital information technology is to create a system of information technology at a level that allows you to solve any strategic tasks, make decisions on the optimal management of socio-economic processes. This will have an impact on the development of the digital economy.

Creating and using new information technology systems is an opportunity to meet existing needs. In this case, all users are actively involved in the promotion of digital information technology.

Today, digital information technology focuses on the mass and rapid processing of information. They should help managers make wise decisions, protect themselves from possible unforeseen events in a changing market, create the conditions necessary to ensure competitiveness, and ultimately succeed.

The rapid introduction of digital information technologies in the national economy and in all spheres of the social sphere is a priority for all countries.

Today, the rapid process of digitization has created a "new economy", ie the digital economy. This little-studied and deep-rooted economy offers great opportunities for producers to organize effective marketing activities in business and social spheres, minimize costs, maximize profits, sell goods and services successfully.

Creating and using new information technology systems is an opportunity to meet existing needs. In this case, all users are actively involved in the promotion of digital information technology.

Today, digital information technology focuses on the mass and rapid processing of information. They should help managers make wise decisions, protect themselves from possible unforeseen events in a changing market, create the conditions necessary to ensure competitiveness, and ultimately succeed.

The introduction of information technology and its rapid development has become one of the main priorities for a number of countries. They are characterized by a long period of digital development, continuity of priorities, from the creation of basic information and communication technologies to the formation of optimal policies in this area and support for the widespread introduction of digital technologies.

In Uzbekistan, 2020 was dedicated to the problems of the digital economy and was declared the "**Year of Science, Enlightenment and Development of the Digital Economy.**" This is very symbolic. In the same year, the full digitization of such areas as transport, geology, education, archives was set. A single electronic system - "**project.gov.uz**" has been introduced for consideration of draft regulations by all interested ministries, departments, local executive authorities, approval (visa issuance) using an electronic digital signature.

At present, an information technology park with modern infrastructure has been built in Tashkent, Nukus, Bukhara, Namangan, Samarkand, Gulistan, Urgench, and in some districts of the regions. The creation of such parks is a prelude to the big steps towards the digital economy.

The new version of the portal "Single interactive public services" on the further development of forms of communication of individuals and legal entities with government agencies in the accelerated development of information technology in the country on the basis of the widespread introduction of the Internet, virtual reception for entrepreneurs - "business.gov.uz" The launch of the .uz portal can be considered as the beginning of important events.

According to the information service of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications, a number of measures have been taken to develop telecommunications infrastructure, including the expansion of trunk telecommunication networks at 237 facilities across the country, modernization of their equipment and interregional transmission capacity of 200 G bit. and 40 Gbit s at the inter-district level. However, all this does not lead to the conclusion that the level of information technology is sufficient.

Uzbekistan ranks 95th in the world in the index of development of information and communication technologies. Our country ranks 129th in the ranking of countries in terms of Internet speed (in this regard, it should be noted that Uzbekistan is twice lower than the average in the Commonwealth of Independent States), 140th in the Index of Economic Freedom.

This means that along with some positive developments in the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, there are many issues that need to be addressed. As the President noted, “Although our country has risen by 8 places in 2019 according to the International Information and Communication Technologies Development Index, we are still far behind. It is also true that most ministries, departments and enterprises are far from digital technologies ”(New Uzbekistan, January 28, 2020, No. 2).

It is no secret that the staff of most sectors of the national economy, even the leaders, as well as our population, do not have the skills to fully understand the nature of the problems associated with the development of information technology and communications. This is another obstacle to accelerating the development of the digital economy.

There are also pending issues in the implementation of online and other types of payments. In 2017, only 34% of account holders in the country made digital payments. This figure is 96 per cent in the UK. It is noteworthy that in our country there are ample opportunities to increase the number of payments through the terminal.

The development of our country, of course, requires special attention to the issues of ensuring close cooperation between government agencies and businesses on the introduction of innovative ideas, technologies and developments, the development of personnel with deep knowledge and intellectual potential.

According to the World Bank, 66% of the world's total wealth falls on human capital, mainly the level of knowledge of the individual. Therefore, in his address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the head of our state emphasized that "the greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest heritage is a good

upbringing, the greatest poverty is ignorance" (// [http://own/politics/zbekiston-respublikasi-president-shovkat-mirziyoev-oliy-25-01-2020](#)).

So, what were the obstacles or problems in the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies in the economy? We have touched on some of them above. However, according to analysts at the consulting service ERGO Research & Advisory, the main problem we have is the telecommunications infrastructure, poor quality of communication and insufficient funds from the state budget.

As a result of low investment in information and communication technologies, the density of base communication stations was low. This leads to the internet, mobile services not working well, resulting in a slowdown in digital economic growth, digital outages. However, the development of information technology can also be caused by the following.

- risk of cyber attack, problems with personal data protection;
- Increasing unemployment, the development of information technology and its implementation may lead to the disappearance of many industries and professions.

Based on the above, we can summarize the following:

- During the years of independence, our country has undergone profound changes in science, including information technology, as a result of which there is a great need for the transition to a digital economy in all sectors of the national economy, and all conditions are created for this;
- When it comes to information technology, it should be noted that information is involved both as a material and as a product;
- information technology - a process that uses a set of means and methods of data collection, processing, transmission to obtain information about the state of an object, process or new feature of the event;
- Information technology is the first basis for the transition to the digital economy. It would be more accurate to call it digital information technology, because information technology is based on relevant numbers.
- Information technology is the basis for the transition to the digital economy, its foundation, the starting point.
- Information technology has become an active force in production, and artificial intelligence has created an opportunity to solve qualitatively new tasks of technical development.

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